

Accepted version of the paper published in: Carballo-Cruz, E., Maroto-Martos, J. C., & Pinos-Navarrete, A. (2024). Overview of touristic innovation in Spain spa tourism. *International Journal of Spa and Wellness*, 7(3), 320-340.

An overview of touristic innovation in Spain spa tourism

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This research analyses the presence of tourism innovation, as a transformation process in spa tourism in Spain. The methodological sequence is: 1) Identification of studies through databases and registers, 2) Analysis of innovation in thermal tourism in Spain, 3) Identification of innovation groups and variables of interest for thermal tourism. Different methods and techniques are used, such as the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses, the Free Word Cloud Generator and the analysis of clusters and concurrences through VOSViewer. The results show the need for a continuous innovation process, since it is used as a temporary stabilizer and not as a source of continuous improvement. The contributions, limitations, and variables on tourism innovation in spa tourism in Spain are identified. In addition, 5 dimensions on how understanding innovation in spa tourism are identified (client profile and satisfaction, innovation objectives, innovation capacities, new or improved products and services, and territorial development). In addition, 30 variables associated with these dimensions are identified, describing the current and future management of innovation in Spanish thermal tourism. As far as we know, this study is the first review on tourism innovation in spa tourism in Spain, establishing a theoretical basis for future studies.

Keywords: spa tourism; tourism innovation; territorial touristic resources

Introduction

The business model and geographical patterns that define thermalism in Western Europe have undergone, as an adaptive response to globalization and post-tourism, profound changes in recent decades (Pinos, Sánchez and Maroto, 2021). Some of these changes are associated with the accelerated demographic aging of societies, which has led administrations to actively promote this process as a means of reducing the health costs derived from sedentary lifestyles and to promote rural development.

Spain is internationally recognized for its abundant mineral-medicinal resources, its tradition in the practice of thermalism for therapeutic purposes and more recently, for its commitment to diversify its offer to orient it to the tourist functionality. In recent decades, treatments based on mineral-medicinal waters with salutary properties have had as their main motivation the cure and/or prevention of health, recovering more recently, other purposes that they had in the 19th century among the wealthy classes that frequented the spas: rest, promoting personal/social relations, recreational and cultural character and even aesthetic improvement. Nowadays for Maroto and Pinos (2019) in Spain there are more than 100 active spas, distributed in 16 Autonomous Communities, demonstrating that the country is an important thermal destination in Europe. The spas have a large associated hotel offer, around 20,000 beds, which positions them as an engine of rural development as they are located, most of them, in rural municipalities.

However, the relationship between supply and demand has been distorted, as have the relationships between the local population and spa visitors (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2010; Pinos, Sánchez and Maroto, 2021). Likewise, it is very alarming that the territory is relegated to the background when this activity is centered, mostly, on thermal establishments with mineral-medicinal waters, and therefore its spatial location has an enormous dependence on the characteristics of the physical environment; in addition to the fact that its continuous operation is highly conditioned by the quality of the natural environment where it is located.

The above, denotes the need for a continuous innovation process that considers the territorial dynamics and the adaptive characteristics that arise from the interaction between supply and demand and that differ from the predominant standardization and homogenization of the thermalism products in the Spanish context. In this case, tourism innovation is an essential means for the development of differentiated products, specialization, diversification of supply and increased quality.

In tourism research, the definitions of Schumpeter (1934), Oslo Manual (OECD, 2005) and Hjalager (2010) are frequently used. Based on the entrepreneurial approach of the former one, innovation is characterized by the creation of new knowledge or new combinations of existing knowledge that are transformed into innovation in the company. Likewise, according to the Oslo Manual (OECD, 2005) and the revisions by Pikkemaat, Peters, & Bichler (2019) there are product, process, marketing and organizational innovations.

In spas, innovation has been mostly directed to the creation of infrastructures and implementation of technologies (Faroldi, et al., 2019). However, its importance for the development of the territories involved and the establishment of synergies to generate new and improved products, services and processes must be considered.

The main objective of this study is to analyze the presence of tourism innovation, as a transformation process, in spa tourism in Spain. To this end, the following questions are proposed: what factors have conditioned the presence of tourism innovation in spa tourism in Spain?; what types and approaches to innovation have predominated in practice?; and what are the fundamental variables to be taken into account in future proposals, according to the review carried out?

Background

This section covers the necessary background for the proposal presentation. It includes innovation approaches to be considered, and general characteristics of the Spa tourism in Spain.

Innovation approaches to be considered in the current work

Innovation is defined differently depending on the research approach. Novelty stands out as a common aspect, since it requires the introduction of something new or substantially improved.

Research on tourism innovation has increased and diversified its topics in recent years (Carballo, et al., 2023; González, Carballo-Cruz, & Carballo-Ramos, 2022; Larrea, Altin, & Koseoglu, 2021; Carballo-Cruz, Betancourt, & Carballo-Ramos, 2021; Cedeño, López, & Zambrano, 2020; Pikkemaat, Peters, & Bichler. 2019), not only because of the impacts generated directly in the sector, but also because of the adaptive effects that this generates in the face of demand reorientations, competitiveness and governance of destinations, post-pandemic tourism, territorial dynamics and sustainable development.

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Pikkemaat, Peters, & Bichler (2019), there are product, process, marketing and organizational innovations.

In addition, it is necessary to consider three approaches to innovation, which coexist with the previously described typologies. These approaches are: innovation capacity in territories and companies, co-creation or open innovation and social innovation (Ramírez & García, 2018; Rodríguez & Quintero, 2019 and García & Palma, 2019).

In this case, both the use of mineral-medicinal waters and the use of contemporary health and beauty techniques constitute resources that need to be diversified and added value from the territory. The above, for creating dynamic innovation capabilities, i.e., focusing on the development of products and services of high current or future demand in spas.

Co-creation or open innovation in thermal tourism involves recognizing the opportunity to co-create products, processes, organizational and marketing practices with clients, employees, public and private organizations, as well as the local population. This, through various forms of collaboration (partnerships, research chairs, crowdsourcing and innovation ecosystems), in addition to the knowledge provided by direct and indirect networks.

On the other hand, social innovation has as its fundamental scenario the territory (García & Palma, 2019) and implies the implementation of new ideas to meet social needs, create new relationships and offer better results. In the case of spas, mineral-medicinal waters or the good practices associated with these, as tourism resources, are embedded in the territory; but paradoxically their development and the participation of local actors has not occupied a leading role.

General characteristics of spa tourism in Spain. Innovation initiatives

Geographical studies and health tourism studies are those that have dealt most profusely with the importance of spas for the socioeconomic development of territories. These studies include research in countries such as Portugal, Argentina, the United States, Ecuador and Brazil (Rodrigues et al., 2022; Patiño & Cabanilla, 2022; Kumar & Sharma, 2020; Gambarota & Lorda, 2019), although it should be noted that in some Latin American countries, such as Peru and Mexico, most of their thermal resources are not inventoried or valued. In Spain, geographical studies predominate and these are

focused on rural areas, mainly in those with demographic problems and tend to depopulation (Maroto and Pinos, 2019).

Thermal tourism in Spain has had different stages. At the end of the 80s of the last century, a reactivation of the same took place, to a large extent, related to the promotion of social thermalism by the IMSERSO (Pilquimán, 2014). This public institution has implemented social tourism programs, mainly oriented to older adults and has set guidelines in the establishment of collaborative relationships between the public and private sector for the reactivation of thermal tourism.

According to Maroto and Pinos (2019), there are more than 100 active spas in Spain, distributed in 16 Autonomous Communities, demonstrating that the country is an important thermal destination in Europe. The spas have a large associated hotel offer, around 20,000 beds, which positions them as an engine of rural development as they are located, most of them, in rural municipalities.

These centers use mineral-medicinal waters to combat different pathologies, to which are added contemporary health and beauty techniques. Their main demand is made up of different user profiles.

With the emergence and expansion of COVID-19, the thermal sector in Spain suffered a significant stagnation, like tourism in general; however, the pandemic evidenced the importance of innovation in tourism companies to stay in the market and generated opportunities for them to show their commitment to social and health responsibility (Pinos & Shaw, 2021).

Examples of innovation initiatives include those aimed at digital marketing or the use of ICTs in the promotion of new online services in spas (Sánchez, 2021; Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya, 2021d); as well as others that border on social innovation, where services are generated to subsidize stays in spas, reopen to health personnel and welcome and accompany elderly people with loneliness and/or health problems. New and/or improved treatments for Covid patients were also introduced. These consisted of inhalation and hydroponic therapies with sulfurous mineral-medicinal waters and respiratory physiotherapeutic intervention against the Covid-19 coronavirus (Pinos & Shaw, 2021).

The renovation of these establishments, the diversification of supply and demand, the new modalities of thermalism and the consideration of the territory as a space for endogenous development; evidence the necessary reactivation of thermal tourism through tourism innovation, however, the lack of studies on the subject is evident, even

more so from an integral and systematic approach. In most cases, innovation is used as a temporary stabilizer through sporadic and emergent improvements or as a synonym of invention, a limitation that needs to be solved in future studies.

Methodology

The methodological sequence of this analysis is carried out from three different but complementary perspectives: 1) Identification of studies through databases and registries, 2) Analysis of the presence of tourism innovation in spa tourism in Spain and 3) Identification of innovation groups and variables of interest for thermal tourism in Spain. Several methods and/or techniques are used in the aforementioned stages to respond to the objective (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Methodological sequence of this research work.

In the first stage, the methodology used was the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) of Page et al. (2021) and the procedure for the analysis is shown, in summary, in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Diagram illustrating the application of the PRISMA method in the context of tourism innovation in thermalism in Spain.

In stage 2, the online tool Free Word Cloud Generator is used to identify the predominant lines of research, in addition to analyzing the contributions, limitations, variables and types of innovation in thermal tourism in Spain. Subsequently, in stage 3, cluster and concurrence analysis using VOSViewer is used to identify key associations and finally, based on the results obtained, components and variables of tourism innovation associated with these are grouped for the development of thermal tourism in Spain.

Analysis of the results

The search was carried out in the first week of May 2024. The Web of Science and Scopus databases were used to identify articles, as they are the most commonly used in systematic reviews, although the information obtained was contrasted with the Google Scholar academic search engine. In this sense, the following search terms were used, considering articles in Spanish and English:

- innovation AND tourism AND thermalism AND Spain
- spa AND tourism AND innovation
- innovation AND thermalism AND Spain
- spa AND tourism AND innovation

Initially, 144 papers were identified, of which 7 were eliminated because they were duplicate entries. The remaining 137 papers, after an analysis of their abstract and keywords, were reduced to 69 articles, 7 of which could not be fully retrieved. Subsequently, the exclusion criteria described in Figure 2 were applied, resulting in a group of 27 papers; these were the studies included in the present review.

Analysis of the presence of tourism innovation in spa tourism in Spain

This section analyses the 27 articles obtained as result of the discussed methodology, mainly focused on the contributions, variables and types of innovation adopted or that can be inferred from the study. In addition, Annex 1 provides a table with the explicit enumeration of such 27 works as well as their main contributions, variables, and innovation types.

Articles from 2011 to 2022 are analyzed (Figure 3) and it is observed that more than 63% of these are from the last 5 years. In this sample, a review prior to the last 10 years is included because it provides unique elements on innovation trends in thermal centers (Henn et al., 2011), especially associated with thermal cosmetics as a new business (product innovation) and its use beyond therapeutic purposes in Galician spas.

Among the keywords identified in Figure 4, a priori, customer and thermal product requirements are visualized, which in a general sense, constitute the attributes of spa tourism in Spain.

According to Carballo-Cruz, Betancourt and Carballo-Ramos (2021), and Carballo et al., (2023), the identification of customer requirements (CR) and product specifications (PS) are of vital importance in tourism innovation, especially that of tourism products. CRs refer to the specific preferences of tourists in the place where the innovation takes place, and the PDs are the attributes or capacities that the establishment and the territory possess to satisfy these preferences with the new or improved products.

Taking into account the contributions of the above-mentioned research, it is evident that exploratory studies predominate and that they provide characteristics of thermalism, thermal centers and resources, as well as the typologies of clients and their profiles; in addition to the need for the use of ICTs and the repositioning of spas after Covid-19.

By regions of Spain, a preponderance of studies from Andalusia (Pilquimán 2014; Pinos, Shaw, & Maroto, 2020; Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; 2021d; Pinos, Abarca & Maroto, 2022) and Galicia (Henn et al, 2011, Alen, De Carlos, & Domínguez, 2014; Amboage, Juanatey & Martínez, 2015; Vallejo, 2015; Rodríguez et al., 2017); although there are also papers that are confined to the regions of Catalonia, specifically Maresme (Torres et al., 2022) and Extremadura (Folgado et al., 2018). The rest of the papers address the subject in a general way.

The most recurrent authors in the thematic treated are Pinos, Shaw & Maroto (2020); Pinos & Shaw (2021) and Pinos, Abarca and Maroto (2022); as well as Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya (2021a, 2021b, 2021c and 2021d). The first group stands out for the variety of their proposals, which highlight the potential of the territory and the thermal centers they analyze as case studies. Likewise, their works are focused on the perceptions of different types of public on the thermal tourism, their opportunities as a health practice during and after the Covid-19; as well as the evolution of the demand and the typologies of clients.

Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya (2021a and 2021b) identify clusters of spas and refer to the functioning of thermal tourism in Andalusia, highlighting the need for rural development based on this activity and the importance of development policies for this purpose.

In Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya (2021c), the factors associated with the level of satisfaction and profile of the spa tourist in Andalusia, southern Spain, are identified. With this work, several attributes or requirements of the client are exposed, overall, for the development of product innovations. Among them, the need for diversification stands out, mainly for young users who demand activities, prices or spaces more appropriate to their preferences and economic possibilities.

On the other hand, focusing on Andalusian spa centers, Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya (2021d) conducted an exploratory study of the contents of websites and uncovered product requirements and specifications, but more oriented towards marketing innovation through the use of ICTs, especially social networks and digital positioning.

Identification of key associations or clusters to be studied

In order to identify clusters of key topics and the relationships between them, an analysis is carried out with the VOSViewer software. This is done by considering the titles and abstracts of the 27 papers considered. Once the process is completed, three fundamental clusters are identified: the first, in green, is associated with the predominant methodologies or approaches of the studies, where spa tourism is one of the elements of greatest concurrence and strength of linkage with other variables. The second and third clusters are related to the attributes or requirements of the spa product.

As shown in Figure 5, the attributes grouped in the lower left cluster describe characteristics of the thermal supply and demand, where spa facilities (facility), customer needs (need), health (health) and information (information) have a higher degree of concurrence and linkage.

Figure 5. Cluster and concurrency analysis of spa tourism in Spain

In the lower right cluster, the attributes or requirements demanded by the client are grouped together, as well as intrinsic elements of the supply. In this cluster, there is a greater concurrence and strength of link between the variables: water resource (water), characteristics of the current demand (demand), the activities carried out in the thermal centers (activity), the impacts generated (impact); as well as the quality of the offer (quality).

Factors limiting tourism innovation in spa tourism in Spain.

In the analysis of the factors that limit the presence of tourism innovation as a tool for the transformation of spas, it should be noted that innovation, despite being a cross-cutting theme, is not among the most common variables in the studies (Figure 3). However, it is recognized as one of the main lines of research in thermal tourism (Antunes, Gonçalves & Estevão, 2022) due to its applicability to various processes such as communication, marketing, continuous improvement and contribution to territorial development.

There is evidence, mostly, of the predominance of descriptive analyses from the supply or demand side (Anaya, Gemar & Anaya, 2021b and 2021c; Folgado et al., 2018), without visualizing the innovation process or the influence of both in the generation of ideas for new or improved products and innovation processes.

Studies on the demand for thermal tourism generally focus on determining the profile of thermal tourists based on their preferences, perceptions and motivations (Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya, 2021a and 2021b; Araújo, Fraiz & Pelegrín, 2021; Monteiro et al., 2022; Pinos, Abarca & Maroto, 2022). In the cited cases, the variables considered are very general and make it difficult to arrive at a contextualized profile for each territory, which limits the promotion, in this way, of differentiation processes through product and marketing innovation.

On the other hand, the studies do not visualize an alignment between rural development through thermal tourism and the need for a process of social innovation. The latter is mentioned as a potential for future studies (Pilquiman, 2013 and 2014).

Despite the preponderance of thermal resources in Andalusia and Galicia, and the evidence of this through several works identified in the discussed methodology, there is no evidence or description of experiences on the creation of clusters or regional groupings to favor innovation and the generation of competitive advantages between territories. With a closer approach, Anaya, Gemar & Anaya (2021a) identify three clusters of spas in Andalusia, Spain, based on a survey of spa users, but this does not lead to a concrete proposal in this regard. This limits and significantly fragments territorial innovation efforts.

In the considered research, studies on the use of social networks and ICTs have an important weight (Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya, 2021d, Sánchez, 2021; Rodríguez et al, 2017; Amboage, Juanatey & Martínez, 2015;), especially for the promotion and positioning of thermal centers. However, from the perspective of tourism innovation, one might ask what incremental or radical improvements this implies in marketing, that is, rather than describing what is currently being done, it would be necessary to focus innovation processes on the creation of dynamic capabilities. It could be done through the incorporation, for example, of group recommender systems, metaverse, internet of

things and business intelligence. Such new trends, still being introduced in some tourism modalities, would be very welcome in the context of spa tourism in Spain.

Dimensions, variables and types of innovation for the development of thermal tourism in Spain

In this section, based on the preceding analyses and supported by the criteria of different authors (Figure 4), 5 clusters or dimensions for tourism innovation in spa tourism in Spain are identified (Figure 6). Likewise, as part of these, 30 variables used in the analyzed studies are identified to address each of the aforementioned dimensions.

Figure 6. Dimensions of tourism innovation for thermal tourism in Spain

Several dimensions include recurrent variables such as: new or improved products, product requirements or specifications, benefits and investments, rural and local development based on tourism, as well as value generation (company and environment) and competitive advantages. Likewise, there are dimensions that are considered as variables within other dimensions such as New or improved products and services as well as Innovation capabilities (Table 1).

Dimensions	Taxonomy of variables that comprise it
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<p>1. Client profile and satisfaction (Kamara, et al., 2017; Del Río, Maldonado y Álvarez, 2018; Pinos, Shaw & Maroto, 2020; Pelegrín, Araújo & Fraiz, 2020; Anaya, Gemar & Anaya, 2021a; 2021b; Araújo, Fraiz & Pelegrín, 2021; Monteiro, et al., 2022 y Pinos, Abarca & Maroto, 2022)</p>	<p>1.1. Motivations of visitors. 1.2. Tourist's preferences. 1.3. Customer requirements. 1.4. Customer satisfaction</p>
<p>2. New or improved products and services (Henn et al., 2011; Pilquiman, 2014; Alina-Cerasela, 2015; Kamara, et al., 2017, Pinos & Shaw, 2021 y Anaya, Gemar & Anaya, 2021a)</p>	<p>2.1. Product requirements or specifications. 2.2. New tourism businesses (thermal cosmetics, gastronomic offers). 2.3. New or improved service protocols (Covid-19). 2.4. New modalities (social thermalism, traditional medicine, relaxation and sustainable naturalness, etc.).</p>
<p>3. Innovation capacities (Kamara, et al., 2017; Del Río, Maldonado y Álvarez, 2018; Gómez et al., 2019; Pinos & Shaw, 2021; Anaya, Gemar & Anaya, 2021a; 2021d; Sánchez, 2021; Antunes, Gonçalves & Estevão, 2022)</p>	<p>3.1 Knowledge generation. 3.2. Implementation of innovation processes. 3.2. Use of ICTs. 3.3. Innovation strategy. 3.4. Technological development. 3.5. Business and financial management. 3.6. Value generation. 3.7. Development policies. 3.8 Strategic communication</p>
<p>4. Innovation objectives (Alen, & Dominguez, 2014; Amboage, Juanatey & Martínez, 2015; Georgescu, et al., 2016; Rodríguez et al., 2017; Anaya, Gemar & Anaya, 2021a; 2021c; Sánchez, 2021)</p>	<p>4. 1. Specialization. 4. 2. Product differentiation. 4. 3. Product diversification. 4. 4. Reactivation of the territory. 4. 5. Digital positioning. 4.6. Profits and investments. 4.7. Rural and local development from tourism.</p>

	<p>4.8. Value generation</p> <p>4.9. Generation of competitive advantages.</p> <p>4.10. Quality improvement.</p>
<p>5 Territorial development (Pilquiman, 2013; 2014; Vallejo , 2015; Kamara, et al., 2017; Folgado et al., 2018; Del Río, Maldonado y Álvarez, 2018; Campón et al., 2020; Anaya, Gemar & Anaya, 2021b; Torres et al., 2022)</p>	<p>5.1 Natural resources (mineral-medicinal waters, landscapes)</p> <p>5.2. Reactivation of the territory.</p> <p>5.3. Sustainable tourism</p> <p>5.4. Sustainable development</p> <p>5.5. Development policies.</p> <p>5.6. Benefits and investments.</p> <p>5.7. Value generation (environment).</p> <p>5.8. New modalities (social thermalism, traditional medicine, relaxation and naturalness).</p> <p>5.9. New or improved products.</p> <p>5.10. Innovation capabilities</p> <p>5.11. Competitive advantages.</p> <p>5.12 Impacts in the rural and local development from the thermal tourism.</p>

On the other hand, the types of innovation with the greatest presence in the studies analyzed, according to the proposals they make, are:

- Product innovation,
- Marketing innovation
- Technological innovation
- Social innovation

Tourism product innovation is one of the most recurrent practices (although it is not explicitly stated). This type of tourism innovation is elucidated in the articles referring to the generation of new or improved products, services, protocols and modalities of thermalism. Likewise, marketing innovation is focused almost exclusively

on digital positioning and the use of ICTs for the promotion of products and, to a lesser extent, for their commercialization through e-commerce.

Process and organizational innovations, despite their necessary application, overlap with the previous ones and, in the best of cases, occur in tandem. It is necessary to point out that the implementation of process innovations in the thermal centers would allow a more integral vision in the resolution of their problems of diversification, commercialization and above all, generation of value and impacts on local development.

On the other hand, social innovation is of great importance for the practice of thermalism in Spain, since its main scenario is the territory and its endogenous development. The proposals analyzed are oriented to the determination of the social impact of thermal tourism (Torres et al., 2022) or more specifically in the thermalism that is developed in rural areas (Pilquiman, 2013 and 2014).

Accordingly, several references are made to the necessary implementation of development policies and social participation; but the design of mechanisms and the implementation of this type of innovation is still limited.

Discussion

Although several works mention and analyze the importance of the territory (Pilquiman, 2013 and 2014; Vallejo, 2015; Kamara, et al., 2017; Folgado et al., 2018; Campón et al., 2020; Torres, et al., 2022), it is essential to consider it beyond the physical space. Instead, it is necessary to focus on the endogenous development policies among communities, being articulated with the efficient use of resources and the existence of territorial clusters.

In territories with consolidated attractions, based on mineral-medicinal waters, with more or less specialization and diversification of this activity, the formation of innovation capacities, co-innovation and differentiation based on local attributes and potentialities is still a pending task; without even glimpsing the necessary social innovation.

Several types of innovation or approaches with this goal are identified in the analyzed works, as for example in Henn et al., (2011); Pilquimán (2014); Amboage,

Juanatey, & Martínez (2015); Pinos & Shaw (2021); Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya (2021); Sánchez (2021); Pinos, Abarca & Maroto (2022), with a greater presence of product innovation and marketing innovation overall, the former with emphasis on the determination of customer profiles and motivations.

Accordingly, this is one of the types of innovation most discussed in the specialized literature on tourism innovation (Hjalager, 2010; Carballo, 2017; Carballo-Cruz, Betancourt, Carballo-Ramos, 2021), however, the linear approach of the proposals still prevails, with an approach focused on supply or the push of demand, where the contexts of innovation (economic, social, environmental, legal, technological), are often relegated to the background, along with local development through thermal tourism.

Specifically for the Spanish spas, the innovation capacities must be identified and generated, being able to allow from the territories, an endogenous and integral development (considering supply and demand variables). These capabilities cannot be ordinary and focused on a series of innovation steps to generate profits at the business level; they must be dynamic innovation capabilities. The latter, derived not from the innovation in the product itself, but from the process of development of the thermal tourism. In other words, it is a question of focusing the attention on the products of current or future demand, which generate greater local synergies and networks between local population, tourist agents and political actors.

However, process innovation is practically not visualized or goes unnoticed in the renovation of spas in Spain. In the works reviewed, it overlaps with marketing innovation, over all, with the use of ICTs and more specifically, with the widespread use of social networks and e-commerce tools, as in Amboage, Juanatey & Martínez, (2015) and Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya (2021c).

There are other factors that hinder the introduction of innovations in the offerings of spas and that need to be considered in future work. Such is the case of the competition of urban establishments over rural ones, which, although they do not use mineral-medicinal waters, their offer is centered on the places where the potential clients reside (hammam or hotel spas).

Likewise, in the Spanish culture, spas are still associated with the elderly and the low influx of young people, which does not favor investments and diversification of the offer according to this segment.

The footprint of innovation in spa tourism in Spain, more than a path to specialization, product diversification and quality improvement, should have a more macro and territorial focus, moving away from massification and towards social innovation. In this sense, spas could be ideal establishments for facilitating the sustainability of their offer, if they were to opt for tourism experiences that follow the slow philosophy. Local actors, especially the resident population, should get involved in the co-creation of tourism experiences that value traditional practices and knowledge as distinctive elements of their territories.

If the spas do not take into account the opinion of the local population and coexist without a relationship, then population would be more resistant to the innovative initiatives of the spas' managers. This is essentially linked to the fact that residents consider that the spa uses a municipal or communal resource (mineral-medicinal waters).

The existing resources in the municipality where the spas are located should complement the thermal offer. Achieving this could favor the uniqueness of each spa and reinforce its territorial identity. Thus, the presence of springs with mineral-medicinal waters can constitute a cultural resource that favors environmental education and territorial knowledge.

Likewise, the establishments where the treatments are given, are usually buildings of historical-artistic heritage, which gives the experience a cultural dimension. However, too few studies regard this dimension (Karama et al., 2017). Also, the characteristics of stays in spas and their average duration facilitate the provision of meals, food that can be local, and this can favor both the reduction of the impacts of the stay and the dynamism of other local productive activities. Thus, tourism innovation can go beyond the main product: the resort, and positively impact other productive support activities, which add distinction to the offer.

Implications, limitations and future research on tourism innovation in spa tourism

The research has revealed the absence of articles, reviews and case studies that analyze the link between tourism innovation and spa tourism in Spain. To the best of our knowledge, the present study is a pioneer in the field.

The contribution of this article lies in its innovative approach in examining the interrelationship between tourism innovation and spa tourism in Spain, using three different methodological perspectives. As results of this analysis, the main limitations with which the subject has been approached are analyzed, among them: the scarcity of research that analyzes the subject in an integral manner. Likewise, five dimensions are identified that describe, to a large extent, the spectrum of innovation in spa tourism in the Spanish context: customer profile and satisfaction, innovation objectives, innovation capabilities, new or improved products and services, and territorial development. Likewise, 30 variables associated with these dimensions are identified that describe the current and future management of innovation in spa tourism in the region.

It has been found that tourism innovation, as a process of transformation of spas and thermal centers, is scarce and the works analyzed present isolated initiatives where innovation is not conceived as a systematic process of creation, but as a sporadic practice and generally associated with the introduction of new technologies or the implementation of ICTs. In these cases, the measurement of its impact on the quality of supply, continuous improvement and local development is still limited.

Likewise, the need for an innovation approach has been identified, where systemic models of this practice are addressed, integrating elements of both demand-driven and technology-driven. In addition, the territorial approach should prevail in the proposals, highlighting especially those elements that enhance the value of spa tourism, not only for health purposes but also for leisure and relaxation. However, innovation should focus not only on the physical aspect of the territory, but also on endogenous and social development policies.

Likewise, the studies reviewed highlight the importance of developing innovation capabilities, especially in terms of product and marketing innovation, but also point to the lack of attention to process innovation, particularly in the renovation of

Spanish spas. Competition from urban establishments, the association of spas with the elderly in Spanish culture and the lack of involvement of the local population are also identified as obstacles to innovation in this sector.

Correspondingly, it is suggested that spas could be ideal centers for promoting sustainability and social innovation, offering tourism experiences that follow the slow philosophy and involve the local population in the creation of such experiences. In addition, the importance of taking advantage of the cultural and natural resources of the municipality where the spas are located to reinforce their territorial identity and uniqueness is highlighted.

On the other hand, this research has significant implications for other resorts in Europe and beyond. First, it highlights the need to adopt a holistic approach that not only focuses on the modernization of facilities and tourism promotion, but also considers the endogenous development of local communities and the preservation of cultural and territorial identity. This perspective may be particularly relevant in Europe, where many spas have a rich history and are rooted in local traditions. Indeed, in Budapest, Hungary, research has shown that international tourists are more attracted to architecture and heritage buildings than to healing waters (Smith, Ferrari & Puczkó, 2016; Smith, Jancsik & Puczkó, 2020).

Furthermore, the emphasis on social innovation and the involvement of local people in the co-creation of tourism experiences could inspire other spa destinations in Europe to rethink their approach towards more sustainable and community-centered tourism. By prioritizing quality over quantity and encouraging a deeper connection between visitors and residents, these spas could differentiate themselves in an increasingly competitive tourism market and offer more authentic and enriching experiences for travelers.

The Spanish experience may provide a valuable model for the positive transformation of other similar destinations in Asia, but which have opted for intensive technological innovation (Soonthodu & Wahab 2022). In this sense, the Spanish model seeks to balance modernization of facilities with preservation of cultural identity and community integration. By prioritizing sustainable practices and focusing on the quality of the experience for visitors, these resorts could differentiate themselves in the global

tourism market and become models of responsible tourism development in their respective regions.

For the development of future research, based on the results of this work, it is necessary to assume that innovation in spa tourism in Spain, beyond its contribution to product specialization and diversification, requires a broader territorial and social approach, promoting the participation of the local community and taking advantage of cultural and natural resources to enrich the tourism offer. In this regard, four lines of future work are identified:

- The exploration of strategies to foster collaboration between resorts and local communities, ensuring acceptance and support for innovation initiatives.

- The integration of cultural and traditional elements in the thermal offer to strengthen the territorial identity and the authenticity of the tourist experience.

- The study of the impact of innovation initiatives on the economic and social development of local communities.

- The differentiation of spas according to the types of innovation that best fit their particular characteristics, such as product, marketing, process, technological and social innovation.

On the other hand, future studies need to broaden the scope of research by exploring a wider variety of literature sources and methodologies, including on-site empirical studies, to obtain a more complete understanding of the evolution of spa tourism at the European and global level.

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Annex 1. Contributions and variables of innovation in thermal tourism in Europe.

Authors/Journal	Contribution	Variables/Innovation types
Henn et al., (2011)/ <i>PASOS: Revista de Turismo y Patrimonio Cultural</i>	Identification of the importance of thermal cosmetics for Galician spas.	Thermal tourism within the concept of health tourism and thermal cosmetics as a new business for Spanish spas. New tourism businesses.
Pilquiman (2013)/ <i>Gran Tour</i>	Study on the implications of spa tourism on rural development in the region.	Territory, resources, rural and local development, implementation of social innovation.

Pilquiman (2014)/ <i>Anuario Turismo y Sociedad,</i>	Aspects of social tourism through thermalism in rural areas in Spain are described.	New or improved products (renovation of thermal establishments, new treatments and the incorporation of recreational thermal programs), diversification of demand, reactivation of the territory, social innovation.
Alen, & Dominguez (2014)/ <i>Current Issues in Tourism,</i>	Analysis of differentiation strategies in thermal tourism establishments in Galicia.	Product differentiation, competitive advantages, product innovation, competitiveness.
Alina-Cerasela (2015)/ <i>Balneo Research Journal</i>	Comparative study of thermal tourism in Spain and Romania	New businesses and modalities, thermal cosmetics, marketing.
Amboage, Juanatey & Martínez (2015)/ <i>Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI). IEEE.</i>	Study on the positioning in social networks of the most representative spas in Galicia using the Fanpage Karma tool.	Use of ICTs, promotion, digital positioning, social networks, innovation in marketing.
Vallejo (2015)/ <i>Agua Y Territorio</i>	Descriptive study on the importance of Galicia's seaside resorts in the first third of the 20th century.	Territory, resources, local development based on thermal tourism.
Georgescu, et al., (2016). In <i>EDULEARN16 Proceedings</i>	Results of the international e-TrawlSpa project aimed at health/wellness and tourism specialists.	Use of ICTs, e-learning, technological innovation, innovation capabilities, requirements for product innovation.
Rodríguez et al., (2017)/ <i>Media and Metamedia Management Springer</i>	Determinants of online visibility, use of ICTs and social networks.	Innovation in marketing, use of ICTs, promotion, etc.
Kamara, et al., (2017)/ <i>Tourism, Culture and Heritage in a Smart Economy Springer, Cham.</i>	It presents the bases and findings for the creation of a cultural map of religious and thermal tourism in a large part of Europe.	Innovation capacity building, product and customer requirements, ICT implementation, religious and thermal potential. Territory.

Folgado et al., (2018)/ <i>Land</i>	Exploratory study of the current tourist use of aquifers in the Spanish region of Extremadura, considering their importance in socioeconomic development and environmental conservation.	Tourism resource (water), territory, sustainable development.
Del Río, Maldonado y Álvarez (2018)/ <i>European Journal of Tourism Research</i>	Bibliometric review of academic studies on thermalism, thalassotherapy and spa.	Visitor motivations (for tourism and therapeutic purposes), knowledge generation, innovation capabilities, business, financial and quality management, marketing innovation, product innovation, customer satisfaction.
Gómez et al., (2019)/ <i>Sustainable Water Resources Management</i>	Study on the traditional techniques and new technologies used in spas.	Technological innovation, combination of techniques and technology, specialization, customer needs, design and implementation.
Pinos, Shaw & Maroto (2020)/ <i>International Journal of Spa and Wellness</i>	The research analyzes the customer profile of the Alhama de Granada spa in Andalusia, Spain. An analysis of the evolution of the demand is carried out, as well as the typologies of the consumer.	Customer profile, customer requirements, tourism demand, new or improved product or offerings, product innovation.
Pelegrín, Araújo & Fraiz (2020)/ <i>Healthcare</i>	Comparative study of the variables explaining purchase intention in spas (wellness tourists and health/medical tourists) using the Cognitive-Affective-Normative (CAN) model.	Customer requirements (pleasure, attention), product requirements associated with performance expectations, product innovation.
Campón et al., (2020)/	Analysis of the tourist	Territory, customer requirements,

<i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health,</i>	experience through the practice of thermal tourism for health purposes, considering its contribution to the quality of life, satisfaction and loyalty of the tourist.	customer satisfaction, sustainable and experiential tourism, motivations and product innovation.
Pinos & Shaw (2021)/ <i>Tourism and Hospitality Research</i>	It presents an analysis of the role and potential of spas as health agents. In the case of Spain, it reflects on the opportunities for a repositioning of this activity in the tourism dynamics that arise during and after Covid-19.	New protocols, post-covid tourist preferences, spa initiatives in the Covid stage, innovation in marketing, use of ICTs, and social innovation.
Anaya, Gemar & Anaya (2021a)/ <i>Sustainability,</i>	Three clusters of spas in Andalusia, Spain are identified from a survey of spa users.	New and improved products (based on identified profiles). New product requirements: diversification of the offer, customer requirements, customer profile, satisfaction of thermal tourist segments. Generation of value and leadership.
Anaya, Gemar & Anaya (2021b)/ <i>Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i>	Study on the current state of the structural and operative functioning of thermal tourism in Andalusia, Spain.	Rural development based on thermal tourism, territory, natural resources, innovation capacities, development policies.
Anaya, Gemar & Anaya (2021c)/ <i>Mathematics,</i>	Identifies the factors associated with the level of satisfaction and profile of the spa tourist in Andalusia, southern Spain.	Thermal tourist profile, customer requirements, satisfaction, product innovation requirements (diversification: attract users with younger profiles).
Anaya, Gemar, & Anaya (2021d)/ <i>Sustainability</i>	Exploratory study of the content in websites of Andalusian spa centers.	Use of ICTs, innovation in marketing: promotion, digital positioning on web sites.

Araújo, Fraiz & Pelegrín (2021)/ <i>Sustainability</i> .	Model for purchase intentions regarding a thermal suite, based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2).	Potential customer profile, product innovation, customer requirements, motivations, etc.
Sánchez (2021)/ <i>Gran Tour, Revista de Investigaciones Turísticas</i> .	Analysis of the online reputation of thermal tourism in Spain.	Innovation in marketing: web visibility, online reputation, travel 2.0 tools, post - Covid-19 communication and positioning strategies.
Monteiro, et al., (2022)/ <i>Marketing and Smart Technologies</i>	Census system that registers the biometric data of the thermalists and stores and prepares them to be processed by any analytical tool with the objective of showing the impact that this sector has on the health of its practitioners.	User or thermalist profiles. Technological innovation.
Pinos, Abarca & Maroto (2022)/ <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i>	A comparative study is made on the current perceptions of thermal tourism among university students in Spain and Germany, using artificial intelligence techniques and qualitative and quantitative methods.	Customer profile, user perceptions to shape new or improved thermal tourism products.
Antunes, Gonçalves & Estevão (2022)/ <i>Geo Journal of Tourism and Geosites</i>	Study on the thermalism in Europe, from a perspective of strategic communication (points out relevant aspects of Spain).	Strategic communication, promotion, innovation as a line of research in thermal tourism.
Torres et al., (2022)/ <i>Plos one</i> ,	Study to evaluate the economic and social value of balneotherapy and thermal	Social innovation, benefits, investments, territory.

	tourism in Maresme, Catalonia, Spain.	
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